

Interventions that support novice nurses' transition into practice: A realist review

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 18 January 2024

Received in revised form 22 April 2024

Accepted 30 April 2024

Available online xxxx

Keywords:

Job satisfaction

Novice nurse

Nurse-sensitive outcomes

Nursing leadership

Nursing workforce

Occupational health

Professional competence

Realist review

Retention

Transition to practice

ABSTRACT

Background: Many transition-to-practice programs have been developed to support novice nurses during their first years into practice. These programs report improvements in retention, wellbeing and clinical competence, but the driving mechanisms of these interventions remain largely unclear.

Objective: To identify how transition-to-practice programs for novice nurses work and in what contexts they work successfully.

Methods: A realist review was conducted. Eligibility criteria included intervention studies aimed at novice nurses in their first two years of practice that reported outcomes on organizational or individual nurse level. The underlying theory of included transition-to-practice programs was extracted, and relevant contextual factors, mechanisms and outcomes were explored and synthesized into context-mechanism-outcome (CMO) configurations. The search was limited to studies between 2000 and 2023.

Results: A total of 32 studies were included, evaluating 30 different transition-to-practice programs with a wide range of intervention components including stress management, clinical education, professional and peer support, and ward rotations. Transition-to-practice programs were often designed without a theoretical foundation. Driving mechanisms behind the programs pertained to psychological, professional, and social development. Contextual factors that activated the mechanisms were enabling conditions for mentors and novice nurses, selection and motivation of novice nurses and organizational culture.

Conclusions: Current transition-to-practice programs primarily focus on the individual and professional development of nurses. However, transition to practice can benefit from a systemic approach that includes development initiatives on the organizational level.

Registration: PROSPERO ID CRD42021268080, August 15, 2021.

Tweetable abstract: Context and mechanisms determine successful implementation of transition to practice programs for novice nurses. @transitiontopractice @nurseworkforce.

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What is already known

- Effective interventions are available to support novice nurses' transition into practice.
- Studies of transition-to-practice interventions to support novice nurses during their first years into practice often have low methodological quality such as lack of concrete indicators or theoretic foundation.

- The driving mechanisms and contextual factors behind transition-to-practice interventions remain largely unclear.

What this paper adds

- An explanatory theory of how transition-to-practice interventions achieve their desired effect was constructed in terms of a context-mechanism-outcome configuration.
- Insight in how transition-to-practice programs for novice nurses work and in what contexts they work successfully.

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- Insight into essential building blocks for developing future transition-to-practice programs.

1. Background

Recruitment and retention of sufficient nurses to ensure safe and high-quality care are key concerns for healthcare organizations (World Health Organization, 2020). However, the transition from nursing student to registered nurse is often difficult. Novice nurses are required to provide safe and high-quality care in a dynamic and complex healthcare system. At the same time, the nursing workforce is dealing with staff shortages while facing the challenge of providing healthcare to a growing elderly population (Wismar et al., 2018). Moreover, novice nurses often feel inadequately prepared for practice (Clark and Holmes, 2007; Kox et al., 2020) and report low levels of self-efficacy regarding their ability to provide care (Monaghan, 2015). As a result, novice nurses frequently experience high workload, resulting in symptoms of stress, burnout, and a high turnover intention (Kox et al., 2020; Laschinger et al., 2009).

Kramer (1975) studied novice nurse challenges during the first year of their careers, and discovered the reality shock that dominates the initial experiences of new graduated nurses. Kramer defines 'reality shock' as the expectation-reality that generates stress and emotions, which are experienced by new graduate nurses during their transition from academia to professional practice in hospitals. Following Kramer, and after years of empirical research, Duchscher (2008) developed the 'transition shock' model which expresses the challenges new graduate nurses face during their transition to professional practice, as a result of the relative contrast between the relationships, roles, responsibilities, knowledge, and performance expectations necessary within the academic environment with those required in professional practice. During the first few months the reality shock is experienced the most intensely due to the initial personal and professional adjustments required.

To prepare novice nurses to work independently in a complex environment and provide high-quality care, various transition-to-practice programs have been developed and implemented. These programs, aimed at facilitating this transition, are required to improve wellbeing of novice nurses in order to reduce turnover, which is in turn associated with improved patient outcomes (Aiken et al., 2021).

The effectiveness of transition-to-practice programs has been identified in several systematic reviews (e.g. Brook et al., 2019; Kenny et al., 2021). Most studies report improvements in retention, wellbeing and clinical competence. However, the methodological quality of included studies is often inadequate for a meta-analysis of shared outcomes. For example, a control group and a clear intervention-outcome match are missing, and driving mechanisms that generate the intended effects remain largely unclear. This paper reports on a realist review that provides a deeper understanding of the driving mechanisms behind interventions that support novice nurse's transition into practice, and contextual factors that affect the effectiveness of these interventions. In contrast to a systematic review or a scoping review, the objective of a realist review is not to create an evaluative overview of the existing literature or present a snapshot of published literature, but to construct an explanatory theory based on the scientific evidence that is currently available (Cook, 2019; Pawson and Tilley, 1997; Pawson et al., 2004). The results are important for developing and implementing new transition-to-practice programs, tailored to specific circumstances and needs of practice. Additionally, the results from this realist review provide directions on what to measure when evaluating existing transition-to-practice programs and thereby contribute to the validity and methodological quality of studies regarding transition-to-practice programs.

2. Method

2.1. Research design

Realist reviews are developed to capture the complex reality in which intervention programs operate in order to identify the mechanisms behind the intervention and the contexts affecting the outcome of the intervention (Pawson and Tilley, 1997; Pawson et al., 2004). Within the conceptual framework of realist reviews, mechanisms are best described as the catalysts behind the desired change or outcome, resulting from an intervention. Contexts on the other hand refer to all environmental factors that influence the outcome of the intervention, for example, the capabilities of the target group or the institution in which the intervention was implemented. Based on the findings of primary intervention studies, realist reviews aim to construct a testable theory in terms of a context-mechanism-outcome configuration of how these interventions achieve their desired effect.

Given the qualitative nature of a realist review, a unanimous decision was made not to assess the methodological quality of the studies included. A judgment on the relevance and rigor of the studies was made instead of using a technical checklist for a particular method, in line with recommendations of the RAMESES research team (Wong et al., 2013).

To ensure transparency in our methodology we uploaded our study protocol to Prospero prior to the start of the search procedure. The protocol was accepted and published on Prospero on August 15, 2021 (protocol code: CRD42021268080).

2.2. Search methods

With support of an academic librarian, search strings were constructed to search for articles that evaluated the effect of a transition-to-practice program aimed at nurses in their first two years of practice. The search was conducted in the databases MEDLINE CINAHL, EMBASE, Web-of-science (Social Science Citation Index), PsycINFO and the Cochrane library. The search was aimed at intervention studies that reported outcomes on the level of the individual nurse (e.g., wellbeing, work-related stress and clinical competence) and/or on the organizational level (e.g., turnover and retention) in either English or Dutch. The search was limited to more recent studies between 2000 and 2021, and was conducted on July 21, 2021, following the methodology (Bramer et al., 2017). This search was updated on July 14, 2023 to verify new publications. Various search terms such as new graduate nurses, transition, leadership, leadership skills, and intervention, training, education, and program were used. The search string is presented in Supplementary File I.

2.3. Selection procedure

Covidence (version v2667 4e921240) was used to organize the realist review process (Covidence systematic review software, Australia). Studies were selected in two stages: title and abstract screening and full-text screening. Studies with a title and abstract that seemed to match our inclusion criteria were selected for full-text screening. Two researchers, blinded for each other's decisions, screened the studies. Conflicting decisions were resolved by a third researcher.

Inclusion criteria were: 1) studies that described the implementation and/or evaluation of a transition-to-practice program aimed at novice nurses in their first two years of practice; 2) an adequate description of the transition-to-practice program; and 3) studies conducted in one of the following settings: hospital care, general practice, mental and public healthcare, emergency departments, intensive care units, and homecare or elderly care. Studies that were conducted in highly specific settings (such as the military) and studies that specifically focused on retention of minority groups or retention of nurses in remote areas were excluded. These exclusion criteria were chosen because of the specific aim of those transition-to-practice programs.

2.4. Data extraction and synthesis

Data extraction and synthesis was reached in several stages. First, two researchers independently extracted information that was considered relevant for construction of the context-mechanism-outcome configurations. The information included intervention components, the theoretic foundation of the intervention, relevant contextual factors, underlying mechanisms and reported outcomes. A third researcher was consulted to dissolve conflicting findings. Next, relevant themes and patterns within the context, mechanisms and outcomes were explored using a thematic analysis approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The findings were refined with feedback from all co-authors. Using the identified themes, context-mechanism-outcome configurations for each individual study were constructed. Finally, a general context-mechanism-outcome configuration was created that summarized the sequence of context, mechanism and outcome elements that are linked together in a meaningful pathway. In order to provide comprehensible pieces of information, the context-mechanism-outcome results are presented per underlying mechanism.

3. Results

3.1. Search outcome

The searches (in 2021 and 2023) yielded a total of 33,197 studies, which were reduced to 15,748 after the removal of duplicate studies (Fig. 1). Restriction of the searches to studies published after 2000 using Covidence resulted in a total of 13,215 studies. Title and abstract screening reduced the number to 555 studies. As a result of full-text screening, 439 studies were excluded. From a total of 116 included studies, 32 studies (9 qualitative, 8 mixed method and 15 quantitative) were included in this realist review as a result of data saturation. In this study, data saturation indicated that the point has been reached where additional studies were unlikely to yield new settings, contextual factors, underlying mechanisms and outcomes. Given the rapidly changing nature of the healthcare landscape due to aging populations and increasing retirement of experienced nurses (Wismar et al., 2018), the

decision was made to start data synthesis in reversed chronological order, starting with the most recent studies (from the first search of 2021 going back in time) (the same strategy was used for the search update in 2023). Moreover, data saturation was likely to be reached before all eligible studies were extracted and therefore including more recent studies was preferred. The included studies were complemented by what we considered exemplary studies, e.g., from Spector et al. (2015) because it reported a large RCT study. The context-mechanism-outcomes of three extra studies were analyzed to ensure no new context-mechanism-outcome themes emerged. The search update finalized the data saturation process.

3.2. Included studies

In the 32 included studies, 30 interventions were evaluated, because the studies of Chesak (Chesak et al., 2019, 2021) and the studies of Dyess (Dyess and Sherman, 2011; Dyess and Parker, 2012) evaluated the same intervention. A total of 21 interventions were included that were complete transition-to-practice programs (Adams et al., 2015; Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Cadmus et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2021; Cline et al., 2017; Dyess and Sherman, 2011; Dyess and Parker, 2012; Eklund et al., 2021; Figueroa et al., 2016; Forde-Johnston, 2017; Gellerstedt et al., 2019; Henderson et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2015; Hussein et al., 2019; Irwin et al., 2021; Mangold and Crockett, 2019; McInnes et al., 2019; Olson-Sitki et al., 2012; Owings and Gaskins, 2020; Phoenix Bittner et al., 2017; Spector et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2019). Nine studied an additional intervention or component (such as mindfulness training) on top of an existing transition-to-practice program (Abiodun et al., 2020; Chesak et al., 2019, 2021; Doughty et al., 2021; Frögéli et al., 2020; Jamieson et al., 2017; Sampson et al., 2019; Stacey et al., 2020; Torres et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2021). Transition-to-practice program interventions included stress management, clinical education, professional and peer support, ward rotations, and personalization in the form of adapting the program to novice nurses' needs and level of competency. Duration of interventions varied from 4 weeks to 12 months. An overview of included studies and intervention characteristics is presented in Table 1.

3.3. Contexts, mechanisms and outcomes

We identified five contextual factors that triggered mechanisms: enabling conditions for novice nurses (e.g. protected time from patient care, employment prospects) and for mentors/preceptors (e.g. training, voluntarily mentorship), selection of participants (e.g. participation is voluntary, selection of the most competent novice nurses), motivation of participants, and organizational culture (e.g. supportive organizational climate or lack of organizational structure). We found three underlying mechanisms that provided the foundation of transition-to-practice programs: professional development (e.g. developing psychomotor skills or learning to reflect), psychological development (e.g. coping or resilience) and social development (e.g. sharing experiences, triumphs and frustrations). Five different outcome categories were identified: professionalism (the conduct, aims or qualities that characterize a professional person (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2023)), nurse wellbeing, sense of belonging, job satisfaction and nurse-sensitive outcomes (e.g. increased retention, staff morale, learning environment). An overview of the contexts, mechanisms and outcomes per included study is presented in Table 2.

3.3.1. Professional development

Professional development as a mechanism was found in 26 studies (covering 25 transition-to-practice programs). A total of 15 professional development theories were used as a foundation for the transition-to-practice programs, with the Novice to Expert Framework being the most prevalent (Benner, 1982) (see Supplementary File II). Professional development included development of reflective skills, including

Fig. 1. PRISMA flow diagram.

Table 1
Overview of selected studies with study descriptors.

Study descriptors					
Author(s); year of publication; country	Design	Setting	Sampling and size	Intervention duration	Intervention characteristics
Abiodun et al. (2020), South Africa	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 76	8 weeks	Peer support
Adams et al. (2015), United States of America	Qualitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 34	6 months	Clinical education Professional support Ward rotation Personalization
Brown Tyo et al. (2018), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 45	28 weeks	Clinical education Professional support Peer support
Cadmus et al. (2023), United States of America	Mixed methods	Acute care rehabilitation facilities Long-term living facilities Assisted living facilities Homecare Insurance agencies Drug rehabilitation networks	Convenience; n = 44	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Ward rotations Stress management Personalization Peer support
Chen et al. (2021), Taiwan	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 293	3 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support Stress management Personalization Stress management
Chesak et al. (2019), United States of America	Qualitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 27	9 months	Stress management
Chesak et al. (2021), United States of America	Mixed methods	Hospital	Convenience; n = 51	12 months	Stress management
Cline et al. (2017), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 1638	12 months	Clinical education
Doughty et al. (2021), New Zealand	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 35	10 months	Clinical education
Dyess and Sherman (2011), United States of America	Mixed methods	Hospital	Convenience; n = 109	10 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support
Dyess and Parker (2012), United States of America	Mixed methods	Hospital	Convenience; n = 89	10 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support
Eklund et al. (2021), Sweden	Qualitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 39	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Stress management Ward rotation
Figueroa et al. (2016), United States of America	Mixed methods	Hospital	Convenience; n = 55	5 months	Clinical education Professional support
Forde-Johnston (2017), United Kingdom	Mixed methods	Hospital	Focus group; n = 26 Convenience; n = 54	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Ward rotation
Frögéli et al. (2020), Sweden	Quantitative	Hospital	Randomized; n = 238	7 weeks	Clinical education Professional support Peer support Stress management
Gellerstedt et al. (2019), Sweden	Qualitative	Hospital	Purposive; n = 19	18 months	Clinical education Professional support Ward rotation
Henderson et al. (2015), Australia	Mixed methods	Hospital	Convenience; n = 78 Focus group; n = 10	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support
Hu et al. (2015), Taiwan	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 107	3 months	Professional support
Hussein et al. (2019), Australia	Qualitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 26	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Ward rotation
Irwin et al. (2021), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 42	10 weeks	Professional support Peer support Stress management Personalization
Jamieson et al. (2017), New Zealand	Qualitative	Hospital	Purposive; n = 7	6 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support Ward rotation
Mangold and Crockett (2019), United States of America	Qualitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 13	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support

Table 1 (continued)

Study descriptors					
Author(s); year of publication; country	Design	Setting	Sampling and size	Intervention duration	Intervention characteristics
McInnes et al. (2019), Australia	Qualitative	General practice	Convenience; n = 18	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Ward rotation
Olson-Sitki et al. (2012), United States of America	Mixed methods	Hospital	Convenience; n = 31	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support
Owings and Gaskins (2020), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 121	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Peer support
Phoenix Bittner et al. (2017), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 24	10 weeks	Clinical education Professional support
Sampson et al. (2019), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Randomized; n = 89	8 weeks	Clinical education Peer support Stress management
Spector et al. (2015), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Randomized; n = 1088	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Ward rotation
Stacey et al. (2020), United Kingdom	Qualitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 60	12 months	Peer support Stress management
Torres et al. (2022), United States of America	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 37	12 months	Professional support Personalization Clinical education Peer support Ward rotation
Xu et al. (2021), China	Quantitative	Hospital	Quasi-randomized; n = 150	4 weeks	Clinical education Professional support
Zhang et al. (2019), China	Quantitative	Hospital	Convenience; n = 438	12 months	Clinical education Professional support Personalization

clinical reasoning and critical thinking (Adams et al., 2015; Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Doughty et al., 2021; Figueroa et al., 2016; Gellerstedt et al., 2019; Hussein et al., 2019; Mangold and Crockett, 2019; Phoenix Bittner et al., 2017; Spector et al., 2015); development of communicative skills (Adams et al., 2015; Cadmus et al., 2023; Dyess and Parker, 2012; Figueroa et al., 2016; Mangold and Crockett, 2019; Spector et al., 2015); development of (interprofessional) collaborative skills (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Cadmus et al., 2023; Figueroa et al., 2016); development of technical or psychomotor skills (Adams et al., 2015; Mangold and Crockett, 2019; Owings and Gaskins, 2020); development of safety and quality competencies (Cadmus et al., 2023; Jamieson et al., 2017); development of personal skills including confidence and self-efficacy (Adams et al., 2015; Cline et al., 2017; Gellerstedt et al., 2019; Hussein et al., 2019; Torres et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2021); and development of organizational skills including delegation and time management (Figueroa et al., 2016). The development of leadership skills was also mentioned and included role development (Adams et al., 2015; Owings and Gaskins, 2020) and skills such as strategic vision, risk-taking and creativity (Cline et al., 2017; Dyess and Sherman, 2011; Dyess and Parker, 2012).

All five contextual factors influenced professional development. For starters, the selection of participants had an influence on professional development. In the study of Adams et al. (2015), novice nurses could only participate in the transition-to-practice program if they already scored high on specific skills and competencies. This led to appreciation of being part of the program, which triggered motivation to develop professionally. This in turn led to increased professionalism regarding working independently and competently. Another contextual factor is the presence of enabling conditions for novice nurses to participate in the transition-to-practice program. In the study of Eklund et al. (2021), novice nurses were offered permanent employment upon entering and all activities in the program were conducted in paid working hours. This also enabled professional development, ultimately leading to professionalism: novice nurses recognizing themselves as registered but novice practitioners. In the study of Hu et al. (2015), enabling

conditions for preceptors were present. All preceptors attended an educational workshop to become familiar with the 10-minute preceptor model intervention. This improved the preceptors' ability to provide daily feedback to novice nurses to enhance skills and knowledge. The motivation of participants was expressed as engagement in the program (Olson-Sitki et al., 2012), or novice nurses appreciating the opportunity to receive training in various specialty areas (Mangold and Crockett, 2019). In contrast, motivation was lower in the study of Brown Tyo et al. (2018), where novice nurses would like to be oriented on one permanent unit. Lastly, organizational culture influenced professional development. For example, one transition-to-practice program focused on providing the best fit between novice nurse and unit (Torres et al., 2022). The units were encouraged to present the best features of their unit culture and give novice nurses a warm welcome upon entering. Novice nurses in return were encouraged to reflect on their opinion of the unit culture and identify personal priorities and values. In other studies, the need for a safe and non-threatening learning environment was stressed (Eklund et al., 2021; Olson-Sitki et al., 2012), e.g., because novice nurses were expected to undertake clinical tasks that they did not feel competent to perform (McInnes et al., 2019).

Professional development led to all outcomes described in Fig. 2 (professionalism, novice nurse wellbeing, job satisfaction, sense of belonging and nurse-sensitive outcomes). Evidently, professional development has an impact on professionalism. Doughty et al. (2021) found that development of patient assessment skills and clinical reasoning increased novice nurses' ability to explain their actions and to interpret information gained from diagnostic tests and problems described by patients. Professional development also impacted novice nurses' wellbeing because possessing relevant competencies decreases stress and anxiety (Chen et al., 2021; Cline et al., 2017; Figueroa et al., 2016; Hu et al., 2015; Owings and Gaskins, 2020; Spector et al., 2015). One study found an increase in stress levels, but no clear explanation was given (Brown Tyo et al., 2018). In some cases, professional development increased nurse-sensitive outcomes. For example, professional development made novice nurses want to continue their current job which had

Table 2
Context-mechanism-outcome analysis of included studies.

Included studies	Context					Mechanism			Outcome				
	Enabling conditions for mentors	Enabling conditions for nurses	Selection of participants	Motivation of participants	Organizational context	Psychological development	Professional development	Social development	Nurse wellbeing	Professionalism	Job satisfaction	Sense of belonging	Nurse-sensitive outcomes
Abiodun et al., 2020		✓		✓				✓				+	
Adams et al., 2015	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			+	+		
Brown Tyo et al., 2018	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	+	+		+	+
Cadmus et al., 2023	✓	✓					✓	✓		+	+	+	+
Chen et al., 2021		✓			✓	✓	✓		+	+			+
Chesak et al., 2019	✓					✓		✓	+	+			
Chesak et al., 2021		✓				✓			+	+			
Cline et al., 2017		✓					✓		+	=	-	-	+
Doughty et al., 2021		✓					✓			+			
Dyess and Sherman, 2011	✓	✓	✓				✓			+	-		+
Dyess and Parker, 2012	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			+			+
Eklund et al., 2021		✓			✓		✓			+			
Figueroa et al., 2016	✓						✓	✓	+	+		+	
Forde-Johnston, 2017			✓				✓	✓		+			
Frögéli et al., 2020		✓				✓			+			+	
Gellerstedt et al., 2019			✓				✓	✓	=	+		+	
Henderson et al., 2015	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	+	+		+	
Hu et al., 2015	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	+	+		+	+
Hussein et al., 2019							✓	✓		+	=	+	+
Irwin et al., 2021				✓		✓		✓	+			+	
Jamieson et al., 2017					✓		✓	✓		+		+	+
Mangold and Crockett, 2019	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓			+		+	
McInnes et al., 2019	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓		+			+
Olson-Sitki et al., 2012		✓		✓	✓			✓		+		+	+
Owings and Gaskins, 2020							✓	✓	+	+	+		+
Phoenix Bittner et al., 2017							✓	✓		+			
Sampson et al., 2019			✓			✓	✓		+		+		
Spector et al., 2015	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	+	+	+		+
Stacey et al., 2020		✓			✓	✓	✓		+	+			+
Torres et al., 2022		✓	✓		✓		✓	✓		+	+	+	+
Xu et al., 2021							✓	✓	+		+		
Zhang et al., 2019	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓					=

Note. '✓', reported; '+', positive changes; '=', mixed changes; '-', negative changes.

Fig. 2. Context-mechanism-outcome configuration with apparent gaps (in orange). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

a positive influence on retention (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Cadmus et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2021; Dyess and Parker, 2012; Hu et al., 2015; Jamieson et al., 2017; McInnes et al., 2019; Owings and Gaskins, 2020; Spector et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2019). Moreover, when nurses developed their leadership skills to change practice, this led to enthusiasm and inspiration within the team to become involved with practice initiatives. Professional development led to a sense of belonging (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Figueroa et al., 2016; Henderson et al., 2015; Hussein et al., 2019; Jamieson et al., 2017; Mangold and Crockett, 2019), but in one case professional development led to a decline in perceived support from staff (Cline et al., 2017). An explanation for this decline may be related to the lack of a preceptor during the first year of practice. Involvement of the team/organization in the training and lectures led to intensive contact with novice nurses, and as a consequence novice nurses developed a bond with their colleagues and developed a sense of belonging in the organization. Finally, professional development had an impact on job satisfaction of novice nurses (Cadmus et al., 2023; Cline et al., 2017; Dyess and Sherman, 2011; Hu et al., 2015; Owings and Gaskins, 2020; Spector et al., 2015).

3.3.2. Psychological development

Psychological development of novice nurses was included in a total of ten studies (covering nine transition-to-practice programs). In total,

nine theories were mentioned as a basis for developing the transition-to-practice program, e.g. the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984), Cognitive Behavior Therapy (Beck, 1970) or Emotional Regulation Systems Model (Gilbert, 2014) (see Table 2). Psychological development of novice nurses included improving individuals' abilities to train their attention and refine interpretations thus influencing stress appraisal (Chesak et al., 2019, 2021; Irwin et al., 2021), off-loading and positively reframing challenging situations (Stacey et al., 2020), monitoring sleep, mood and depression (Chen et al., 2021), engagement in proactive behaviors (Frögéli et al., 2020), improving cognitive beliefs about their ability to manage stress and healthy lifestyle choices (Sampson et al., 2019) and improving coping skills (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Dyess and Parker, 2012).

The psychological development of novice nurses is influenced by all five contextual factors. A factor most commonly found is that of protected time from patient care, an enabling condition for novice nurses (Chesak et al., 2021; Dyess and Parker, 2012; Frögéli et al., 2020; Stacey et al., 2020). This protected time allows novice nurses to fully focus on the contents of the intervention. For example, in the study of Chesak et al. (2021) novice nurses were allowed protected time from patient care and were compensated with their usual salary rate. This helped them to focus on training their attention and refining interpretations, which influenced their stress appraisal. This ultimately

led to reduced stress and improved resilience and mindfulness. Another common factor is that of trained preceptors/mentors, an enabling condition for mentors (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2021; Chesak et al., 2019; Dyess and Parker, 2012). Interventions that focus on psychological development often require specialized knowledge about psychological processes. This means that mentors/preceptors often have to undergo (a short) training in order to support or counsel novice nurses properly. For example, in the study of Chen et al. (2021) mentors were required to have at least 12 h of teaching ability training in order to properly monitor sleep, mood and depression of the novice nurses while also counseling and supporting them throughout the intervention. This eventually increased novice nurse retention, and improved wellbeing and professionalism. Organizational culture also influenced psychological development. The study by Stacey et al. (2020) showed that a lack of organizational structure for addressing problems of novice nurses caused concern among preceptors. They felt that the preceptees held an expectation that the preceptors would fix any problem, however there was vagueness around how these issues should be escalated within the organization and thus led to unsolved problems. Other factors such as making intervention participation voluntary, a method of selecting participants (Sampson et al., 2019), influenced psychological development in the sense that novice nurses could decide themselves whether they needed or wanted to participate in the mental health intervention. Adherence to the program and assigned homework (Frögéli et al., 2020) stimulated psychological development, leading to positive outcomes. Lastly, the motivation of participants also played a role in the psychological development of novice nurses (Irwin et al., 2021).

Outcomes related to the psychological development of novice nurses encompassed wellbeing, professionalism, sense of belonging, nurse-sensitive outcomes and job satisfaction. Psychological development influenced the wellbeing of novice nurses. Improvements in mood, self-care, resilience, mindfulness and a reduction in perceived stress were found (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2021; Chesak et al., 2019, 2021; Frögéli et al., 2020; Irwin et al., 2021; Sampson et al., 2019; Stacey et al., 2020). Outcomes on professionalism include acting out compassion toward peers, colleagues and into patient care (Stacey et al., 2020), and novice nurses were more mindful of the task at hand and paid more attention to details, rather than being distracted by other thoughts (Chesak et al., 2019). Nurse-sensitive outcomes related to the program function as a vehicle to challenge the workplace culture (Stacey et al., 2020), increased patient safety (Brown Tyo et al., 2018) or increased retention rates (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2021; Dyess and Parker, 2012). Lastly, outcomes related to sense of belonging (Brown Tyo et al., 2018; Frögéli et al., 2020) and job satisfaction (Sampson et al., 2019) were found.

3.3.3. Social development

In total, 19 transition-to-practice programs used social development as a mechanism to support transition to practice of novice nurses. Frögéli et al. (2020) based their transition-to-practice program on the Organizational Socialization Framework, the other transition-to-practice programs had no theoretic foundation linked to social development (see Table 2). Social development as a mechanism referred to novice nurses getting acclimated to the work environment (Brown Tyo et al., 2018), enhancement of professional relationships and inter-professional interaction (Figueroa et al., 2016; Forde-Johnston, 2017; Jamieson et al., 2017; Torres et al., 2022) and sharing experiences with peers or mentors/preceptors and support each other (Abiodun et al., 2020; Cadmus et al., 2023; Chesak et al., 2019; Gellerstedt et al., 2019; Henderson et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2015; Hussein et al., 2019; Irwin et al., 2021; Mangold and Crockett, 2019; McInnes et al., 2019; Olson-Sitki et al., 2012; Owings and Gaskins, 2020; Spector et al., 2015; Torres et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2019).

All five contextual factors affect social development. A relevant contextual factor was that the novice nurse and coach were matched (an

enabling condition for novice nurses) (Mangold and Crockett, 2019). It was important that the novice nurse and coach shared the same patients, so they were able to work together closely and frequently. This enabled a coaching process which led to a sense of belonging and professionalism. In some out-of-hospital settings, few novice nurses are hired which created a challenge in connecting with other novice nurses in the organization (a constraining condition for novice nurses) (Cadmus et al., 2023). Another relevant contextual factor was organizational culture. The study of Jamieson et al. (2017) highlighted a strong team ethos in supporting each other and the novice nurses. This triggered relationship-building and led to a sense of belonging in the organization, professionalism and nurse-sensitive outcomes. Lastly, the motivation of participants was found to be a relevant contextual factor. In the study of Olson-Sitki et al. (2012) novice nurses were highly engaged in the program. They shared common experiences, making them realize they were not isolated in their experiences. This understanding led to a better connection between novice nurses across departments and created shared stories and humor, and deeper enculturation into the organizational environment. Enabling conditions for mentors, like provision of training and selecting competent mentors, triggered social development (Zhang et al., 2019). Mentors successfully provided encouragement, guidance, and support for novice nurses in terms of difficulties in the first year of nursing. The relationship between mentor and mentee was seen as fundamental for psychological and social support. Lastly, participant selection was a contextual factor for social development. In one study (Spector et al., 2015) participation was voluntary; in another study (Brown Tyo et al., 2018), strict selection criteria were applied. This influenced the amount and type of novice nurses that participated in the transition-to-practice programs and profited from social development mechanisms.

Social development contributed to all five outcomes described. Sense of belonging was the most often mentioned outcome. For example, in the study of Abiodun et al. (2020), an online community of practice stimulated and facilitated interaction with other professionals and peers. As a result, novice nurses reported feeling part of a professional team. An example of social development leading to nurse-sensitive outcomes (retention) was provided by McInnes et al. (2019). In this transition-to-practice program designed for general practice, mentors provided novice nurses with support, inspired, and increased passion for general practice. This increased the desire to continue working in that setting. In the study of Hussein et al. (2019) job satisfaction was enhanced by effective relationships with supervisors. Ineffective relationships led to lower job satisfaction. A good example of the link between social development and novice nurse wellbeing was provided by Gellerstedt et al. (2019). Novice nurses reported that they lacked a preceptor for confirmation, dialog and encouragement. This caused feelings of stress. However other novice nurses reported feeling relieved to think and act independently. Finally, Chesak et al. (2019) focused on mindfulness and resilience training. They found that discussing stressful situations with other nurses who have been in similar situations validated their feelings and empowered novice nurses to more effectively respond to stressful situations. This helped to reduce stress at the end of a workday. The program also improved personal growth (mindfulness, presence, gratitude and compassion) and had a positive impact on relationships with family, friends, patients and coworkers. A good example of how social development influenced professionalism was provided by Gellerstedt et al. (2019). They found that dialog, encouragement and feedback from supervisors increased novice nurses' confidence and professional performance. In addition, sharing experiences with the trainee group enhanced their development, because talking to someone outside the ward provided them with an outside perspective.

To summarize the findings, a general context-mechanism-outcome configuration was drafted (Fig. 2), adapted from Mathisen et al. (2022). The figure explains how constraining and enabling contextual factors in the healthcare organizations impact mechanisms that determine whether transition-to-practice programs will produce the intended outcomes. The

figure includes apparent gaps, as described in the discussion section, in order to provide an extensive framing of our complete findings. This, however, does not mean that the figure is complete, as there may be other gaps that we have not found.

4. Discussion

This realist review aimed to identify how transition-to-practice programs for novice nurses work and in what contexts they work successfully. The results provide insight into essential building blocks for developing future transition-to-practice programs. This adds to the study of [Kenny et al. \(2021\)](#) describing the need for conceptual clarity on transition-to-practice and that it is unclear to which extent novice nurses' professional and personal needs are supported in the transition. The transition-to-practice programs in our study reflected three categories of development: professional, psychological, and social development, each of which supports novice nurses in overlapping or different ways during their transition to professional practice. These findings extend on previous work by [Brook et al. \(2019\)](#), which shows that a combination of elements that focus on building competence and confidence, such as teaching, with those that focus on socialization and embedding the new nurse into the work environment, such as mentoring or preceptorship, may be effective at retaining nurses.

Whereas most studies made use of a theoretical framework, in approximately 41 % ($n = 13$) of the interventions no clear underlying theory was mentioned. This is worrisome because to understand the mechanisms that make an intervention work, a clear underlying theory is necessary ([Pawson and Tilley, 1997](#); [van Hooft et al., 2017](#)). An underlying theory provides suggestions about how to address problems, and also how to interpret outcomes related to the intervention used ([Kivunja, 2018](#)).

The results of our study show that nursing leadership theories are still rarely applied in transition-to-practice programs. Of the studies in this review, only three made use of nursing leadership strategies in their interventions ([Cline et al., 2017](#); [Dyess and Sherman, 2011](#); [Dyess and Parker, 2012](#)). Literature shows that when nursing leadership skills are developed in novice nurses this can support transition to practice, through increasing influence over their practice environment ([Dyess and Sherman, 2011](#)). This can promote a more satisfying professional career. Moreover, leadership skills support novice nurses to lead change in order to deal with the increasing complexity of health care and the ever-changing environment of nursing. A focus on nursing leadership corresponds with the Bachelor of Nursing 2030 ([Bouwes et al., 2023](#)), the new nursing education profile in Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands, using the CanMEDS ([Royal College, 2015](#)) roles as foundation. BN2030 emphasizes the competencies needed to prepare future nurses to meet the demands placed on them in the field of leadership: personal and professional development (including professional identity) and positioning. These competencies are deemed crucial in order to act decisively and to position future nurses as an equal partner in professional consultation. After graduation, transition-to-practice programs can build on this by further stimulating development of these leadership competencies in novice nurses.

By influencing their working environment, novice nurses will be able to (to a certain extent) personalize their own transition to practice based on their skills and needs. As it stands, only a handful of included studies allowed for a certain degree of personalization in their interventions ([Adams et al., 2015](#); [Chen et al., 2021](#); [Irwin et al., 2021](#); [Zhang et al., 2019](#)). These studies included personalization in the form of allowing novice nurses additional time to transition, adjusting the intervention to the individual's learning style, making use of an individualized resilience toolbox or developing a personalized career plan for every novice nurse. Some included studies adopted the strategy for novice nurses to choose their own mentor/preceptor ([Dyess and Sherman, 2011](#); [Dyess and Parker, 2012](#); [Zhang et al., 2019](#)). However, there was no mention of an intervention that could be fully personalized to the individual's skills and needs.

A surprising finding in this review was that little attention was paid to physical development. Only one study included changing cognitions about lifestyle in their transition-to-practice program ([Sampson et al., 2019](#)). Nursing is a physically demanding profession that requires strength, endurance, and dexterity to perform tasks effectively. Therefore, it is important for novice nurses to develop physically, so that they are fit and are able to handle the physical requirements of the profession better. [Kox et al. \(2023\)](#) found that musculoskeletal symptoms contribute as a statistically significant predictor to dropout among novice nurses and students. Physical activity has potentially beneficial effects for mental wellbeing, improving self-esteem, cognitive functioning, worker's capacity to adapt to work conditions, and absenteeism while reducing anxiety, lower back pain and turnover ([Biddle and Asare, 2011](#); [Craft and Landers, 1998](#); [National Research Council, 1999](#)). Physical development might prove a useful component in transition-to-practice programs, but additional research is needed to prove whether this is truly the case.

An interesting finding is that the reviewed studies primarily concentrate on the individual nurse's development, and only a minority of studies paid attention to a healthy work environment within their transition-to-practice program designs ([Eklund et al., 2021](#); [Figueroa et al., 2016](#); [Henderson et al., 2015](#); [Hussein et al., 2019](#); [Olson-Sitki et al., 2012](#); [Torres et al., 2022](#)). However, research has shown that a healthy work environment plays a crucial role during the transition of novice nurses ([Kramer et al., 2013](#)) and predicts novice nurses' organizational commitment ([Rush et al., 2019](#)). Factors such as authentic leadership, structural empowerment and person-job fit have been found to significantly impact job and career satisfaction, as well as turnover intention among nurses ([Spence Laschinger et al., 2018](#)). Psychological safety also emerges as a critical element for novice nurses during their transition ([Lyman et al., 2020](#)). Building credibility, establishing personal connections, feeling supported, and having a sense of safety are all important for their successful integration into nursing practice. Creating an environment that supports novice nurses in their transition requires substantial commitment from organizations. This includes providing necessary resources, fostering healthy practice environments, and promoting good leadership. Furthermore, it is worth noting that an environment supportive of novice nurses' transition has been linked to improved collaborative workplaces, higher retention rates, and better patient outcomes. Multiple studies have demonstrated the positive impact of supportive work environments on nursing practice and overall organizational performance ([Aiken et al., 2014](#); [Dawson et al., 2014](#); [Purdy et al., 2010](#)).

4.1. Strengths and limitations

A strength of this realist review is the thorough examination of available interventions to ensure saturation. Although not all eligible studies were included, the research team carefully reviewed the available literature to ensure that data saturation was achieved. In addition, it is important to note that saturation was also achieved for the setting variable. The remaining studies were carefully examined to identify any new settings, and only two studies included new settings (e.g. home care, drug rehabilitation). While this process contributes to the strength of the study's methodology, it is a limitation in terms of the generalizability of the findings, as the focus of the studies was primarily on transition-to-practice programs in the hospital setting. Another strength is the inclusion of multiple components and outcomes in the review of transition-to-practice programs. This comprehensive approach allows for a broader understanding of the interventions and their effects. However, a limitation is the difficulty in disentangling specific context-mechanism-outcome relationships. Due to the complexity of the programs included in the review, it was challenging to establish clear links between specific mechanisms and outcomes. This limitation suggests that further research may be necessary to better understand the specific pathways through which these complex interventions lead to outcomes.

4.2. Implications for practice

The findings of this realist review have important implications for practice. In contrast to common practice, selecting only the most competent nurses for transition-to-practice programs has significant disadvantages. In fact, particularly less experienced nurses can greatly benefit from transition-to-practice programs. This finding has significant implications for organizations facing nurse shortages, as it suggests that a broader approach to recruitment and retention can be adopted.

One practical implication is the integration of a baseline assessment to measure the novice nurse's starting point at the beginning of the transition-to-practice program. By doing this, organizations can identify the specific needs and skill shortages of individual nurses. This approach enables a tailored and personalized development plan that addresses the unique requirements of each novice nurse. Moving away from a one-size-fits-all approach allows organizations to provide targeted support and resources, enhancing the effectiveness of the transition-to-practice program. This way, high-performing novice nurses who aspire to go above and beyond can also benefit from transition-to-practice programs. By offering advanced modules or additional opportunities for growth, organizations can serve the needs and ambitions of these high-flyers. This approach not only enhances their professional development but also contributes to their job satisfaction and overall engagement within the organization.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of considering not only the individual level but also the team and organizational aspects when implementing transition-to-practice programs. While the focus of transition-to-practice programs is typically placed on the development of individual nurses, successful integration of young nurses into the workforce requires a systemic approach. It is evident that a top-down implementation of transition-to-practice programs is insufficient, and a comprehensive, systemic perspective is necessary. To effectively address the challenges and maximize the benefits of transition-to-practice programs, a holistic approach that acknowledges the interplay between individual, team, and organizational factors is essential. By embracing this systemic approach, healthcare organizations can better support the transition and development of novice nurses, ultimately leading to improved patient outcomes and enhanced workforce sustainability. This study also highlights the need for continued theoretical foundation to achieve high quality nursing research. Whereas the majority of the included studies provided a theoretical foundation for their transition-to-practice programs, a large proportion did not.

Funding

This publication is part of the project 'Een vitale start in de praktijk voor stagiaires en beginnende verpleegkundigen - Leren van goede praktijken' with project number RAAK.PUB11.053 of the research programme RAAK-publiek which is financed by the Dutch Research Council (NWO). Taskforce for Applied Research SIA (Regieorgaan SIA).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

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Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Kim J. Verhaegh:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank W.M. Bramer and M. Engel from the Erasmus MC Medical Library for developing and updating the search strategies. The authors also thank M.C. de Wit for his assistance in writing the Prospero protocol and J. Auxier for improving the use of English in the manuscript.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2024.104785>.

References

- Abiodun, R., Daniels, F., Pimmer, D.C., Chipps, J., 2020. A whatsapp community of practice to support new graduate nurses in South Africa. *Nurse Educ. Pract.* 46, 102826. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102826>.
- Adams, J.M., Alexander, G.A., Chisari, R.G., Banister, G., McAuley, M.E., Whitney, K.B., Erickson, J.I., 2015. Strengthening new graduate nurse residency programs in critical care: recommendations from nurse residents and organizational stakeholders. *J. Contin. Educ. Nurs.* 46 (1), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00220124-20151217-01>.
- Aiken, L.H., Sloane, D.M., Bruyneel, L., Van den Heede, K., Griffiths, P., Busse, R., ... RN4CAST consortium, 2014. Nurse staffing and education and hospital mortality in nine European countries: a retrospective observational study. *Lancet (Lond., Engl.)* 383 (9931), 1824–1830. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62631-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62631-8).
- Aiken, L.H., Simonetti, M., Sloane, D.M., Cerón, C., Soto, P., Bravo, D., ... Lake, E.T., 2021. Hospital nurse staffing and patient outcomes in Chile: a multilevel cross-sectional study. *Lancet Glob. Health* 9 (8), e1145–e1153. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(21\)00209-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(21)00209-6).
- Beck, A.T., 1970. Cognitive therapy: nature and relation to behavior therapy. *Behav. Ther.* 1 (2), 184–200. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-7894\(70\)80030-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-7894(70)80030-2).
- Benner, P., 1982. From novice to expert. *Am. J. Nurs.* 82 (3), 402–407.
- Biddle, S.J.H., Asare, M., 2011. Physical activity and mental health in children and adolescents: a review of reviews. *Br. J. Sports Med.* 45 (11), 886–895. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2011-090185>.
- Bouwes, A., Broekman, H., Dobber, J., Eisenberg, I., den Hertog, R., Rutgers, A., 2023. Opleidingsprofiel bachelor nursing 2030. Retrieved from <https://www.loov-hbov.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/2023-10-16-BN2030def.pdf>.
- Bramer, W.M., Rethlefsen, M.L., Kleijnen, J., Franco, O.H., 2017. Optimal database combinations for literature searches in systematic reviews: a prospective exploratory study. *Syst. Rev.* 6 (1), 245–y. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-017-0644-y>.
- Braun, V., Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual. Res. Psychol.* 3, 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>.
- Brook, J., Aitken, L., Webb, R., MacLaren, J., Salmon, D., 2019. Characteristics of successful interventions to reduce turnover and increase retention of early career nurses: a systematic review. *Int. J. Nurs. Stud.* 91, 47–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2018.11.003>.
- Brown Tyo, M., Gundlach, M., Brennan, C., Esdale, L., Knight, A., Provencher, S., Tardy, K., 2018. Leading the charge: achievement of national accreditation for a nurse residency program. *J. Nurses Prof. Dev.* 34 (5), 270–276. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NND.0000000000000476>.
- Cadmus, E., Bohnarczyk, N., de Cordova, P.B., 2023. Transition into practice: beyond hospital walls. *J. Contin. Educ. Nurs.* 54 (7), 327–336.
- Chen, S., Fang, Y., Wang, M., Wang, T., 2021. Effects of an adaptive education program on the learning, mental health and work intentions of new graduate nurses. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 18 (11), 5891. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18115891>.
- Chesak, S.S., Morin, K.H., Cutshall, S., Carlson, M., Joswiak, M.E., Ridgeway, J.L., ... Sood, A., 2019. Stress management and resiliency training in a nurse residency program: findings from participant focus groups. *J. Nurses Prof. Dev.* 35 (6), 337–343. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NND.0000000000000589>.
- Chesak, S.S., Morin, K.H., Cutshall, S.M., Jenkins, S.M., Sood, A., 2021. Feasibility and efficacy of integrating resiliency training into a pilot nurse residency program. *Nurse Educ. Pract.* 50, 102959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102959>.
- Clark, T., Holmes, S., 2007. Fit for practice? An exploration of the development of newly qualified nurses using focus groups. *Int. J. Nurs. Stud.* 44 (7), 1210–1220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2006.05.010>.
- Cline, D., La Frenz, K., Fellman, B., Summers, B., Brassil, K., 2017. Longitudinal outcomes of an institutionally developed nurse residency program. *J. Nurs. Adm.* 47 (7/8), 384–390. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNA.0000000000000500>.

- Cook, D.A., 2019. Systematic and nonsystematic reviews: choosing an approach. *Healthcare Simulation Research: A Practical Guide*, pp. 55–60.
- Craft, L.L., Landers, D.M., 1998. The effect of exercise on clinical depression and depression resulting from mental illness: a meta-analysis. *J. Sport Exerc. Psychol.* 20, 339–357.
- Dawson, A.J., Stasa, H., Roche, M.A., Homer, C.S.E., Duffield, C., 2014. Nursing churn and turnover in Australian hospitals: nurses' perceptions and suggestions for supportive strategies. *BMC Nurs.* 13 (1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6955-13-11>.
- Doughty, L., Sinnema, C., McKillop, A., Dixon, R., 2021. The impact of postgraduate education in transition to practice programmes on new graduate nurses' knowledge and skills: a pre-post survey design. *Nurse Educ. Today* 102, 104888. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2021.104888>.
- Duchscher, J.B., 2008. A process of becoming: the stages of new nursing graduate professional role transition. *J. Contin. Educ. Nurs.* 39 (10), 441–450.
- Dyess, S., Parker, C.G., 2012. Transition support for the newly licensed nurse: a programme that made a difference. *J. Nurs. Manag.* 20 (5), 615–623. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2834.2012.01330.x>.
- Dyess, S., Sherman, R., 2011. Developing the leadership skills of new graduates to influence practice environments: a novice nurse leadership program. *Nurs. Adm. Q.* 35 (4), 313–322. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NAQ.0b013e31822ed1d9>.
- Eklund, A., Billett, S., Skyvell Nilsson, M., 2021. A bridge over troubled water? - exploring learning processes in a transition program with newly graduated nurses. *Nurse Educ. Pract.* 51, 102982. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2021.102982>.
- Figueroa, S., Gardner, J., Irizarry, J., Cohn, T., 2016. Married state preceptorship model: crossing the state line in new graduate nurse transition to practice. *J. Contin. Educ. Nurs.* 47 (11), 511–517. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00220124-20161017-10>.
- Forde-Johnston, C., 2017. Developing and evaluating a foundation preceptorship programme for newly qualified nurses. *Nurs. Stand.* 31 (42), 42–52. <https://doi.org/10.7748/ns.2017.e10413>.
- Frögéli, E., Rudman, A., Ljótsson, B., Gustavsson, P., 2020. Preventing stress-related ill health among new registered nurses by supporting engagement in proactive behaviors—a randomized controlled trial. *Worldviews Evid.-Based Nurs.* 17 (3), 202–212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12442>.
- Gellerstedt, L., Moquist, A., Roos, A., Karin, B., Craftman, Å.G., 2019. Newly graduated nurses' experiences of a trainee programme regarding the introduction process and leadership in a hospital setting—a qualitative interview study. *J. Clin. Nurs.* 28 (9–10), 1685–1694. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.14733>.
- Gilbert, P., 2014. The origins and nature of compassion focused therapy. *Br. J. Clin. Psychol.* 53 (1), 6–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjc.12043>.
- Henderson, A., Ossenberg, C., Tyler, S., 2015. 'What matters to graduates': an evaluation of a structured clinical support program for newly graduated nurses. *Nurse Educ. Pract.* 15 (3), 225–231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2015.01.009>.
- van Hoof, S.M., Been-Dahmen, J.M.J., Ista, E., van Staa, A., Boeije, H.R., 2017. A realist review: what do nurse-led self-management interventions achieve for outpatients with a chronic condition? *J. Adv. Nurs.* 73 (6), 1255–1271. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13189>.
- Hu, Y., Chen, S., Chen, L., Shen, H., Lin, Y., Chang, W., 2015. Evaluation of work stress, turnover intention, work experience, and satisfaction with preceptors of new graduate nurses using a 10-minute preceptor model. *J. Contin. Educ. Nurs.* 46 (6), 261–271. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00220124-20150518-02>.
- Hussein, R., Salamonson, Y., Everrett, B., Hu, W., Ramjan, L.M., 2019. Good clinical support transforms the experience of new graduates and promotes quality care: a qualitative study. *J. Nurs. Manag.* 27 (8), 1809–1817. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.12880>.
- Irwin, K.M., Saathoff, A., Janz, D.A., Long, C., 2021. Resiliency program for new graduate nurses. *J. Nurses Prof. Dev.* 37 (1), 35–39. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NND.0000000000000678>.
- Jamieson, I., Sims, D., Casey, M., Wilkinson, K., Osborne, R., 2017. Utilising the Canterbury dedicated education unit model of teaching and learning to support graduate nurses. *Nurs. Pract. N. Z.* 33, 29–39. <https://doi.org/10.36951/NgPxNZ.2017.008>.
- Kenny, A., Dickson-Swift, V., McKenna, L., Charette, M., Rush, K.L., Stacey, G., ... Phillips, C., 2021. Interventions to support graduate nurse transition to practice and associated outcomes: a systematic review. *Nurse Educ. Today* 100, 104860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2021.104860>.
- Kivunja, C., 2018. Distinguishing between theory, theoretical framework, and conceptual framework: a systematic review of lessons from the field. *Int. J. Higher Educ.* 7, 44. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v7n6p44>.
- Kox, J.H.A.M., Groenewoud, J.H., Bakker, E.J.M., Bierma-Zeinstra, S., Runhaar, J., Miedema, H.S., Roelofs, P.D.D.M., 2020. Reasons why dutch novice nurses leave nursing: a qualitative approach. *Nurse Educ. Pract.* 47, 102848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102848>.
- Kox, J.H.A.M., van der Zwan, J.S., Groenewoud, J.H., Runhaar, J., Bierma-Zeinstra, S., Bakker, E.J.M., ... Roelofs, P.D.D.M., 2023. Predicting late dropout from nursing education or early dropout from the profession. *Sci. Talks* 5, 100106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitalk.2022.100106>.
- Kramer, M., 1975. REALITY SHOCK: why nurses leave nursing. *Am. J. Nurs.* 75 (5) Retrieved from https://journals.lww.com/ajnonline/fulltext/1975/05000/reality_shock_why_nurses_leave_nursing.41.aspx.
- Kramer, M., Brewer, B.B., Maguire, P., 2013. Impact of healthy work environments on new graduate nurses' environmental reality shock. *West. J. Nurs. Res.* 35 (3), 348–383. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193945911403939>.
- Laschinger, H.K.S., Finegan, J., Wilk, P., 2009. New graduate burnout: the impact of professional practice environment, workplace civility, and empowerment. *Nurs. Econ.* 27 (6), 377–383.
- Lazarus, R.S., Folkman, S., 1984. Stress, Appraisal, and Coping. Springer Publishing Company Retrieved from <https://books.google.nl/books?id=i-ySQQQuUpr8C>.
- Lyman, B., Gunn, M., Mendon, C., 2020. New graduate registered nurses' experiences with psychological safety. *J. Nurs. Manag.* 28. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13006>.
- Mangold, K., Crockett, C.C., 2019. Supporting the transition to practice for nurse residents on a multispecialty unit. *Crit. Care Nurse* 39 (5), 76–79. <https://doi.org/10.4037/cncn2019165>.
- Mathisen, C., Heyn, L.G., Jacobsen, T., Bjørk, I.T., Hansen, E.H., 2022. The use of practice education facilitators to strengthen the clinical learning environment for nursing students: a realist review. *Int. J. Nurs. Stud.* 134, 104258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2022.104258>.
- McInnes, S., Halcomb, E., Huckel, K., Ashley, C., 2019. Experiences of registered nurses in a general practice-based new graduate program: a qualitative study. *Aust. J. Prim. Health* 25 (4), 366–373. <https://doi.org/10.1071/PY19089>.
- Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2023. Professionalism. Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/professionalism>.
- Monaghan, T., 2015. A critical analysis of the literature and theoretical perspectives on theory-practice gap amongst newly qualified nurses within the United Kingdom. *Nurse Educ. Today* 35 (8), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.03.006>.
- National Research Council, 1999. *Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders: Report, Workshop Summary, and Workshop Papers*.
- Olson-Sitki, K., Wendler, M.C., Forbes, G., 2012. Evaluating the impact of a nurse residency program for newly graduated registered nurses. *J. Nurses Staff Dev.: JNSD: Off. J. Natl. Nurs. Staff Dev. Org.* 28 (4), 156–162. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NND.0b013e31825dfb4c>.
- Owings, C.R., Gaskins, S.W., 2020. Evaluation of a community-based nurse residency. *J. Nurses Prof. Dev.* 36 (4), 185–190. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NND.0000000000000646>.
- Pawson, R., Tilley, N., 1997. *Realistic Evaluation*. Sage Publications, Inc, Thousand Oaks, CA, US.
- Pawson, R., Greenhalgh, T., Harvey, G., Walshe, K., 2004. *Realist synthesis: an introduction. RMP Methods Paper 2/2004*.
- Phoenix Bittner, N., Gravlin, G., MacDonald, C., Bourgeois, D., 2017. A newly licensed nurse orientation program evaluation: focus on outcomes. *J. Contin. Educ. Nurs.* 48 (1), 22–28. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00220124-20170110-07>.
- Purdy, N., Spence Laschinger, H.K., Finegan, J., Kerr, M., Olivera, F., 2010. Effects of work environments on nurse and patient outcomes. *J. Nurs. Manag.* 18 (8), 901–913. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2834.2010.01172.x>.
- Royal College, 2015. *CanMEDS*. Retrieved from <https://www.royalcollege.ca/en/canmeds.html>.
- Rush, K.L., Janke, R., Duchscher, J.E., Phillips, R., Kaur, S., 2019. Best practices of formal new graduate transition programs: an integrative review. *Int. J. Nurs. Stud.* 94, 139–158.
- Sampson, M., Melynk, B.M., Hoying, J., 2019. Intervention effects of the MINDBODYSTRONG cognitive behavioral skills building program on newly licensed registered nurses' mental health, healthy lifestyle behaviors, and job satisfaction. *J. Nurs. Adm.* 49 (10), 487–495. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNA.0000000000000792>.
- Spector, N., Blegen, M.A., Silvestre, J., Barnsteiner, J., Lynn, M.R., Ulrich, B., ... Alexander, M., 2015. Transition to practice study in hospital settings. *J. Nurs. Regul.* 5 (4), 24–38. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2155-8256\(15\)30031-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2155-8256(15)30031-4).
- Spence Laschinger, H.K., Wong, C., Read, E., Cummings, G., Leiter, M., Macphee, M., ... Wood, K., 2018. Predictors of new graduate nurses' health over the first 4 years of practice. *Nurs. Open* 6 (2), 245–259. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nop.2.231>.
- Stacey, G., Cook, G., Aubeeluck, A., Stranks, B., Long, L., Krepa, M., Lucre, K., 2020. The implementation of resilience based clinical supervision to support transition to practice in newly qualified healthcare professionals. *Nurse Educ. Today* 94, 104564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2020.104564>.
- Torres, D.A., Jeske, L., Marzinski, S.J., Oleson, R., Hook, M.L., 2022. Best fit orientation: an innovative strategy to onboard newly licensed nurses. *J. Nurses Prof. Dev.* 38 (6), 350–359.
- Wismar, M., Maier, C.B., Sagan, A., Glinos, I.A., 2018. Overlaps in Europe's health workforce: addressing the conundrums. *Eurohealth* 24 (2), 38–42 Retrieved from <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/332571>.
- Wong, G., Greenhalgh, T., Westhorp, G., Buckingham, J., Pawson, R., 2013. RAMESES publication standards: realist syntheses. *BMC Med.* 11, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7015-11-21>.
- World Health Organization, 2020. *State of the world's nursing report 2020: investing in education, jobs and leadership*. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003279>.
- Xu, F., Ma, L., Wang, Y., Yu, J., Li, D., Zhou, G., ... Cao, Y., 2021. Effects of an innovative training program for new graduate registered nurses: a comparison study. *SAGE Open* 11 (1), 2158244020988542. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020988542>.
- Zhang, Y., Huang, X., Xu, S., Xu, C., Feng, X., Jin, J., 2019. Can a one-on-one mentorship program reduce the turnover rate of new graduate nurses in China? A longitudinal study. *Nurse Educ. Pract.* 40, 102616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.08.010>.